

Attitude of Parents towards Social Acceptance of Visually Impaired Children in Rural Area of South 24 Parganas

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ABSTRACT : The study attempts to investigate the attitude of parents towards social acceptance of visually impaired children. The study also aims to find out the levels of difference among the attitude of different sub category of parents towards visually impaired children. Parental attitude scale has been constructed on the basis of Likert's 5 point scale. It consists of two sub-scales (i. Caring attitude and ii. Discriminating attitude). Data were collected from 70 parents under 8 Circle Level Resource Rooms and analyzed by using descriptive statistics and ANOVA. The result indicates that the parents have positive attitude towards the social acceptance of visually impaired children. However parental attitude towards social acceptance of visually impaired children is affected by their education and occupation.

Keywords : Attitude, Parents, Social Acceptance and Visually Impaired Child.

Introduction

Visual impairment is a sensory exceptionality (vision problem). The individual receives impressions of the world only through the sense organs. More impressions reach to the brain through the sense of sight than through all other senses combined. Thus visual difficulties may influence the life of the individual in the physical, mental, social, educational and vocational

aspects. According to the *Rehabilitation Council of India Act 1992*: visually handicapped means a person who suffers from any of the following conditions, namely:

- i) Total absence of light.
- ii) Visual acuity not exceeding 20/200 (Snellen) in the better eye with the correcting lenses, or

- iii) Limitation of field of vision subtending an angle of 20 degree or worse. (S.K.Mangal, Chapter-7, P-179)

Low Vision: A person with impairment of visual functioning even after treatment or standard refractive correction but who uses or is potentially capable of using vision for the planning or execution of a task with appropriate assistive device. [Defined by the Persons with Disability Act, 1995]

American Medical Association: “*Blindness* is central visual acuity for distance of 20/200 or less in the better eye with correction or, if greater than 20/200, a field of vision not greater than 20 degrees at the widest diameter” (Hatfield, 1975, pp 3-20). There are 600 million people with disabilities in the world (UN Report, 2003). According to “World Library and Information Congress: 73rd IFLA General Conference and Council 19th to 23rd August 2007 Durban, South Africa”- total visually challenged population in India = 10.6 million, in West Bengal= 0.86 million. According to state elementary education report card: 2010-2011; number of V.I. (Blind) students in West Bengal at Primary & Upper Primary level is 8209; and number of V.I. (Low Vision) students in West Bengal at Primary & Upper Primary level is 22309.

National Elementary Education Report Card 2011-12 shows that total number of Visually Impaired Students = 38,242 (Blind = 9075 & Low Vision = 29,167);

National Elementary Education Report Card 2012-13 shows that total number of Visually Impaired Students = 37815 (Blind = 7796 & Low Vision = 30019);

National Elementary Education Report Card 2013-14 shows that total number of Visually

Impaired Students = 34563 (Blind = 6962 & Low Vision = 27601);

The first special school in the World to teach blind children was “*The Institute Royale Des Juenes Aveugles*” in Paris. *Valentin Hauy* was founded in 1784 and the first special school in India for blind students was set up in Amritsar in the year 1887 by Miss. Annie Sharp, a Christian Missionary from England.

Still now our society makes discrimination between non-disabled child and disabled child. Social improvement cannot be possible except the inclusion of disabled children in the process of socialization. They are the part of our society. The constitution of India ensures equality, freedom, justice and dignity of all individuals and implicitly mandates an inclusive society for all persons with disabilities.

The appropriate government and local authorities shall ensure that all children with disabilities shall have an equal basis with all other children, a right to freely express their views on all matters affecting them; and provide them appropriate support for the exercise of this right. (The Draft Rights of Persons with Disabilities Bill, 2012) and also mention the guiding principal

d) Respect for difference and acceptance of persons with disabilities as part of human diversity and humanity; *h)* Respect for the evolving capacities of children with disabilities and respect for the right of children with disabilities to preserve their identities.

Still now our society cannot accept visually impaired children. Some parents show positive attitude for acceptance of Visually Impaired children. They provide all facility equally for their

children and some do not and as a result, we don't know the present status of acceptance of visually impaired children.

Purpose of the Study:

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the attitude of parents towards social acceptance of visually impaired children in rural area of south 24 parganas and also aimed to find out the difference among the parents of different groups of occupational category and educational category. The main objective of this study was "To find out the attitude of teachers towards social acceptance of Visually Impaired Students".

Hypotheses:

HO1. There will be no significant difference in caring attitude towards Visually Impaired Children among the parents of different groups of occupational category (Service, Farming & Daily Labour).

HO2. There will be no significant difference in discriminating attitude towards Visually Impaired Children among the parents of different groups of occupational category (Service, Farming & Daily Labour).

HO3. There will be no significant difference in caring attitude towards Visually Impaired Children among the category of parent's qualification (Class VII pass, Class VIII- MP and HS - Graduation).

HO4. There will be no significant difference in discriminating attitude towards Visually Impaired Children among the category of parent's qualification (Class VII pass, Class VIII- MP and HS - Graduation).

Methodology:

The descriptive survey method was used in the present study.

Variables:

The present researchers had identified one major variable-

1. Parental Attitude

Categorical Variable:

- i. Occupation and ii. Educational Qualification

Population and sample:

The investigator collected the data from teachers who enlisted their visually impaired children in Circle Level Resource Room (CLRC). 70 parents of visually impaired children were taken in this regard.

Tools:

Researchers had used self-made attitude scale "Parental Attitude scale towards social acceptance of Visually Impaired children (PASSAVIC)" to measure parental attitude. There was two sub scales for measuring - i) Caring Attitude and ii) Discriminating Attitude. The parental Attitude scale consisted of 22 items (i. Caring Attitude-10 items and Discriminating Attitude-12). The categories of responses were 'strongly agree'; 'agree'; 'undecided'; 'disagree'; 'strongly disagree' and '5'; '4'; '3'; '2'; '1' were the respective scores awarded for the responses. Some items were negative in nature and the scoring was done in reverse order i.e. '1'; '2'; '3'; '4'; '5' in those cases. Reliability of the scale '**Caring Attitude of Parents-(CAP)**' was computed by using Cronbach's Alpha through SPSS 20.0 version and was found 0.838 and it has a good alpha

value and it was acceptable and Reliability of the scale ‘**Discriminating Attitude of Parents-(DAP)**’ was computed by using Cronbach’s Alpha through SPSS 20.0 version and was found 0.801 and it has a good alpha value and it was acceptable.

Collection of data:

The researchers first contacted with Special Educators of various resource rooms (circle of South 24 Parganas) for obtaining the data regarding Visually Impaired Students (i.e. name, address and parent’s name). With the help of the Special educators, the researchers contacted the parents to get necessary permission from them and then collected data by administering Attitude Scale.

Analysis of Data and Interpretation:

The study consisted of quantitative analysis using descriptive statistics. After collection of data researchers coded number against every item of attitude scale and calculate the total score of each participant. All the raw data were tabulated in MS excel and further analysis were done in SPSS 20.0 version by importing data from excel file. Researchers employed descriptive statistics like percentage, Mean, S.D., also ANOVA for analysis of data.

O. To find out the attitude of parents

towards social acceptance of Visually Impaired Students.

Table. 1. Description of attitude of parents_ PASSAVIC

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Caring Attitude	70	34.76	5.666
Discriminating Attitude	70	41.74	6.752
Total Attitude	70	76.50	11.24

While estimating the mean value of PASSAVIC from the data that collected from the Parents of Visually Impaired Children at different CLRC, it has found 76.50 (table: 01.) In PASSAVIC scale a respondent can score 22 to 110. So, it can be said that, parents of Visually Impaired child possess a moderate positive attitude towards Social acceptance of Visually Impaired Child.

To fulfill the objective, four null hypotheses were formulated and tested which were as follows:

HO1. There will be no significant difference in caring attitude towards Visually Impaired Children among the parents of different groups of occupational category (Service, Farming & Daily Labour)

From the analyses in **Table 02** it shows that the $F_{(2,67)}$ is 1.721 and p value is 0.187 ($p > .05$).

Table 2. Occupation of Parents (CAP)_ ANOVA

Caring Attitude	Sub-scale	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Between Groups	108.247	2	54.123	1.721**	.187
	Within Groups	2106.624	67	31.442		
	Total	2214.871	69			

**not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Hence 'F' is not significant at 0.05 level. So, **Ho1** is not rejected and it can be safely said that there were no significant difference among occupational category of parents in respect to their attitude towards caring of visually impaired children.

HO2. There will be no significant difference in discriminating attitude towards Visually Impaired Children among the parents of different groups of occupational category (Service, Farming & Daily Labour).

In case of comparing the groups of parents considering the effect of occupation (Service;

Farming & Daily labour; Business) in their discriminating attitude, the analysis in the **table-3 shows** that calculated $F_{(2,67)}$ is 5.740 and $P=0.005$ ($p<0.05$). Hence 'F' is significant at 0.05 level. So **Ho2** is rejected and it can be said that there is significant difference among the groups in their attitude of caring towards visually impaired children. From the subsequent Post Hoc Analysis for multiple comparison, it is seen from **table-4** that significant difference exists between "Service" and "Farming & Daily labour" (Mean difference=8.599 and $P=0.004$) groups and "Service" and "Business" (Mean Difference = 8.366 and $P=0.014$) groups.

Table 3. Occupation of Parents (DAP)_ANOVA

	Sub-scale	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Discriminating Attitude	Between Groups	460.081	2	230.041	5.740*	.005
	Within Groups	2685.290	67	40.079		
	Total	3145.371	69			

*Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Post Hoc Test-

Table 4. Multiple Comparisons _Group Wise

Dependent Variable	Occupation of parents-(i)	Occupation of parents-(j)	Mean difference (i-j)	Std. Error	Sig.
Discriminating Attitude	Service	Farming & Daily Labour	8.599	2.565	.004
		Business	8.366	2.869	.014

*Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 5. Description of Discriminating Attitude

Discriminating Attitude	Occupation	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Service	49.428	4.649
	Farming & Daily Labour	40.829	6.627
	Business	41.062	5.971

HO3. . There will be no significant difference in caring attitude towards Visually Impaired Children among the category of parent's qualification (Class VII pass, Class VIII- MP and HS - Graduation).

From the analyses in **Table 06** it is seen that the $F_{(2,67)}$ is 2.33 and p value is 0.105 ($p > .05$). Hence 'F' is not significant at 0.05 level. So, **Ho3** is not rejected and it can be safely said that there were no significant difference among the parents of different groups based on educational qualification.

HO4. There will be no significant difference in discriminating attitude towards Visually Impaired Children among the category of parent's qualification (Class VII pass, Class VIII- MP and HS - Graduation).

the parents of different groups based on their educational qualification.

Discussion

The present study was aimed to determine the Parental attitude towards the social acceptance of visually impaired children in rural area of south 24 parganas. Result of this study suggests that parents of visually impaired children showed positive attitude towards social acceptance. Lakshmi *et al.* (2009) highlight the fact that the parents of the visually impaired children attending the integrated schools, showed a favourable attitude towards the teaching aspect in integrated school and Thengal (2013) found that the parents and family members have positive attitude towards mentally retarded

Table 6. Qualification of Parents (CAP)_ ANOVA

Caring Attitude	Sub-scale	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Between Groups	144.243	2	72.122	2.334**	0.105
	Within Groups	2070.628	67	30.905		

**not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 7. Qualification of Parents (DAP)_ ANOVA

Discriminating Attitude	Sub-scale	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Between Groups	132.427	2	66.213	1.472**	.237
	Within Groups	3012.945	67	44.969		
	Total	3145.371	69			

**Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

From the analyses in **Table 07** it is seen that the $F_{(2,67)}$ is 1.472 and p value is 0.237 ($p > .05$). Hence 'F' is not significant at 0.05 level. So, **Ho4** is not rejected and it can be safely said that there were no significant difference among

children. These findings support the present findings. Though Arora (2010) found negative parental attitude leads to rejecting attitude towards mentally retarded children. This adversely affects the interaction within the

family and also with outsiders. This cannot support the findings of the present study.

In respect of occupational status all parents showed positive attitude towards discrimination of visually impaired children. The service category (parents) showed very high positive attitude than the two other categories, i.e., Business category (parents), & Farming and daily labour category (parents). They want to accept visually impaired children as like as other children in our society. Again this study suggests that parents of visually impaired children showed moderately positive attitude towards social acceptance. In respect of qualification/ educational status, parents showed positive attitude towards caring and discrimination of visually impaired children. Service category (parents) showed high positive attitude than Business category (parents), Farming and daily labour (parents). They want to accept visually impaired children as like as other children in our society.

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